

Optical system for automatic color monitoring in heterogeneous media during vinification processes

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Abstract

Wine is one of the most important food products worldwide. However, the application of technologies to the winemaking process can improve. An RGBC optical sensor, used to measure color intensity and shade, was developed and tested in real environments. It is able to measure samples without filtering by offering the color intensity and shade of a filtered sample. Color intensity can be measured within the range of 1.5 and 9.5 color points with an approximate 3% error. The model for shade can be applied to red wines with an approximate 1% error. It can operate directly in cellars under real operating conditions. It avoids collecting samples, and filtering and measuring in a spectrophotometer. It opens the door to automatic and continuous color and shade measurements by increasing knowledge of the process, reducing the cost of analytics and offering enologists a tool to improve wine quality.

Keywords: optoelectronic nose, sensor, wine, color intensity, shade

1. Introduction

Wine is a global product of high economic relevance. According to the International Organization of Vine and Wine (OIV, 2017), Spain occupies a relevant position in the international wine economy. In 2016, Spain had the largest area of vineyards (975 thousand hectares), was the third producer of wine and must (39.3 million hectoliters), and the biggest exporter of wine worldwide in volume terms (22.9 million hectoliters). Despite being the biggest exporter, the price per liter of exported Spanish wine was lower than that of countries such as Italy and France. Furthermore, globalization, and the emergence of new competitors such as New Zealand, Chile, Australia and South Africa, mean that it is necessary to develop new techniques to improve both wine production and quality, as well as yields in the treatments applied during the winemaking process.

Although improvement to the fermentation process is one of the most relevant aspects to obtain quality wines of higher values, relevant changes can be observed even after completing alcoholic fermentation. This part of the process is characterized by long time periods during which the alcoholic mixture continues to undergo changes that alter both its chemical composition and appearance. For example, the main compounds in young red wines responsible for their color are anthocyanin pigments, which progressively disappear as they are degraded and transformed into more stable pigments, which would influence the color of more complex wines (García-Puente Rivas et al., 2006). Thus, wine continues to be periodically supervised by enologists.

Among the main wine attributes, color is the first attribute perceived by consumers. It provides information about virtues or defects, the preparation method and its evolution over the years. From a technological point of view, the study of color differences and their determination is most interesting in numerous winemaking-related operations, such as wine blends (coupages).

It is a parameter that varies due to the important role played by climate conditions. These conditions can vastly differ one year to the next, and can modify grape composition. In fact highly positive correlations have been obtained between color and overall wine quality (Casassa and Sari, 2007). Consequently, the possibility of reliably monitoring wine's color evolution during processes would provide enologists with valuable information during not only fermentation, but also throughout all stages in wineries.

During winemaking, color and shade measurements, which are the most relevant parameters, are generally made by winemakers off line with a spectrophotometer by measuring absorbance at different wavelengths. Unfortunately, this procedure is difficult to automate as it is necessary to extract a sample, filter it prior to measuring and have a spectrophotometer. This leads to a limited number of measurements being made in warehouses, despite the interest in monitoring such an important parameter. In recent years, several studies have emerged that aim to develop new analysis methods for simpler wine monitoring (Cetó et al., 2012). They use various techniques, but probably the most suitable ones for practical uses are those based on optical systems. These measurements do not require coming into direct contact with the sample, which avoids the sensor from deteriorating and legislation restrictions. In addition, the development of LEDs, microelectronics and the ability to process and send information, provides robust, simple, sensitive and cheap devices that operate remotely and can automate processes.

Undoubtedly in the near future, the use of portable optical systems, with one sensor connected to a microprocessor that stores data, could become popular in the winemaking world. As it is a very precise low-cost tool that is easy to use and couple with other equipment and automation systems, research is being conducted to approach technology to industry's requirements (Batistell et al., 2014), in particular the agri-food sector, where it has the potential to optimize the control and security of processes. Furthermore, these tools can be applied in parallel with

other developing technologies, such as electric pulses (El Darra et al., 2016), or the use of pectolytic enzymes (Romero-Cascales et al., 2012), to improve the color of wines.

With optical sensors, systems based on diode arrays can be used to analyze and control products as they move through different transformation process stages. They can also be applied to classify products into categories, and they offer a range of qualities that meet the expectations of different consumers and optimize the production value. Finally, they allow defects to be detected that can lead to products being discarded. Although some optical systems have already been implemented into several sectors, very few applications are used in warehouses (Jiménez-Márquez et al., 2014). One example of combining an optical array with a camera has been explored to simulate sensorial analyses and to detect possible fraud or adulteration in wines (Chung et al., 2015). Chemical reagents or indicator membranes can also be coupled to fiber optic systems to determine specific parameters, such as sulfur dioxide (Monro et al., 2012; Stangelmayer et al., 1998). One particular sensor that takes advantage of the simultaneous analysis of light with diverse wavelengths for viticulture uses a nondestructive fluorescence-based technique to evaluate grape maturity. It provides indices of anthocyanins and chlorophyll in red grapes, and also of flavonols and chlorophyll in white grapes (Agati et al., 2013). For wine-aging purposes, a system with a combination of two optical fibers capable of measuring at diverse wavelengths has been used to determine refractive index, color and shade (Noiseux et al., 2004). A smartphone camera, used as an acquisition device, has been employed to monitor the browning process in wines due to the presence of furfural compounds (Pérez-Bernal et al., 2017). The quantification of phenolic compounds during vinification in the red winemaking process has been addressed by Fourier transform mid-infrared (FT-MIR) spectroscopy and chemometrics (Fragoso et al., 2011). Jiménez-Márquez et al. (2013 and 2014) have developed diverse devices to measure fermentation kinetics by means of refractive index measurements using a laser diode and a position-sensitive detector. Wine maceration has been followed by

absorbance measurements within the visible spectrum with LEDs and photodiodes for color measurements.

However, it should be stressed that both must and wine are highly colored before clarification, rather than inhomogeneous fluids of a turbid nature, which contain a large amount of colored suspended particles in motion that come in a variety of sizes. In fact the turbidity for a finished wine is usually very low, and is below 1 or 2 NTUs in most cases. However, values as high as 2000 NTUs can be reached during the winemaking process, which is a very wide measuring range (García et al., 2008). Thus most of the aforementioned systems, particularly those that measure the interaction with light within the visible range with transmission techniques, are not useful for directly monitoring the maceration, fermentation and/or aging processes of wine because they need a filtration step prior to measurements. It limits their direct applicability in industries, and makes the possibility of automating color measurements difficult in wine cellars.

Based on our ample experience in developing optical sensors (McGaughey et al., 2006; Moragues et al., 2014; Zaragoza et al., 2015), we present an optical sensor to measure color and shade in wine that is capable of overcoming the above-mentioned limitations. It can operate directly in cellars under real operating conditions and avoids having to collect samples. It opens the door to automatic continuous color and shade measurements by increasing the control of the process, reducing the cost of analytics and offering enologists a tool to improve wine quality.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Origin of wine samples

All the measurements were taken in two different tank types at the Bodega La Viña (D.O. Valencia), Spain. They include stainless steel tanks that can hold 250 m³ and 25-m³ concrete tanks. Samples were randomly selected from the samples that were to be analyzed by

warehouse personnel. They were all finished wines which had undergone malolactic fermentation, and had been clarified and cold-stabilized.

2.2 Measuring wine samples by reference techniques

The Glories method was used as a reference technique to characterize color intensity (CI) and shade in samples (Method OIV-MA-AS2-07B). This spectrophotometric method is widely employed by enologists (Negueruela et al., 1995) because it is fast, reliable and simple. It has already been used by other authors to measure the color of finished red wines in previous works (Noiseux et al., 2004). CI and shade were calculated from the absorbances at 420, 520 and 620 nm, and also by simple arithmetic calculation. CI was the addition of the absorbances at 420, 520 and 620 nm. Shade was the quotient between the absorbances at 420 nm and 520 nm (Method OIV-MA-AS2-07B). For the reference analysis, samples were collected from tanks as close as possible to the optical sensor. Their temperature was recorded immediately after being removed from tanks by a TP-10 probe, which was inserted directly into the beaker that contained wine. They were centrifuged for 5 minutes at 3500 rpm (Selecta Centrolit II-BL) before taking measurements to remove solids in suspension. A UV/VIS ONDA Mod.UV-20, a 1mm optic path cell and distilled water as a blank were used to collect the absorbances at 420, 520 and 620 nm (International Organisation of vine and wine, 2011). The absorbance values were multiplied by 10 to obtain the value of a standard 10 mm cell. pH measurements were taken by a Crimson pHmeter. The alcoholic volume was measured by density determination. All the samples and measurements were taken in duplicate.

2.3 The optical sensor's hardware and software

The optical sensor was based on the photodiode array TAOS model Adafruit TCS3472. Figure 1a shows the optical sensor (a 1 euro coin was included in the photo to compare size). The TCS3472 device provides a digital return of red (R), green (G), blue (B) and clear light (C) sensing values. The receptor is composed of an array of 12 photodiodes. 9 are selective for each of the RGB

parameters: 3 blue ($I_{\max} = 465$ nm, spectral halfwidth 22 nm), 3 green ($I_{\max} = 525$ nm, spectral halfwidth 35 nm) and 3 red ($I_{\max} = 615$ nm, spectral halfwidth 15 nm). Furthermore, three photodiodes without color filter (clear) are included. The device integrates a microcontroller that averages the RGB values of all the photodiodes of the same color and of the clear ones. An IR blocking filter, integrated on-chip and localized to the color sensing photodiodes, minimizes the IR spectral component of incoming light and allows color measurements to be accurately taken. The high sensitivity, wide dynamic range and IR blocking filter make the TCS3472 an ideal color sensor solution to be used under varying lighting conditions and through attenuating materials. The color sensor includes not only the detector but also a LED type light source. The LED source is a EVERLIGHT, 45-21/QK2C-B3845AC2CB2/2T with light emission wavelengths from 400 to 750 nm that covers the visible zone and an emission zone of 3,8 mm². Light has a color rendering index (CRI) of 75, a color temperature (CTT) between 3800 to 4500 °K, values of luminous intensity (Iv) from 1800 to 2200 mcd and Φ Typ. equal to 6.2 lm. Capturing the RGB-C values occurs after illuminating the sample, so the value reflected in it is measured in relation to the employed light source. The sensor has four 16-bit analog/digital converters and one digital output via a I2C interface. The sensor is controlled by a microcontroller (ATMEL-ATMEGA 32UA) connected, on the one hand, to the photodiode matrix sensor and, on the other hand, to a computer via a USB connection. It sends the measured and filtered values of the four analyzed components to the computer: Red, Green, Blue and Clear. The computer is responsible for providing this information to the user both visually and storing it in text files for further processing. The sensor was controlled by an Arduino-based software facilitated by the sensor provider. Data collection, format modification and storage in a CSV file were done by the researchers.

A plastic adapter was prepared to measure samples, which fitted the sensor to the cylindrical pipeline, and the whole system was held to the pipe by elastic to avoid movements while measuring took place. Two pipes of the same kind were used. Figure 1 shows the optical sensor

and the electronic system implemented in the pipeline. As we can see, the small dimensions of the sensors and electronics facilitates implementation in industrial environments and imply no significant variations in installations.

2.4 Data acquisition

To take measurements, a tubular glass window (ITA-ITA DN80, Figure 1c) was placed at the tank entrance. The external pipeline part was cleaned before the pipe was placed. The sensor was surrounded by a black plastic to avoid external lights interfering while taking measurements. For each sample, the sensor collected approximately 150 measurements in the presence of solids in suspension for 60 seconds.

2.5 Data analysis

Our system has a high level of complexity due to the combination of diverse media (liquid flowing inside the walls of the peephole) with the high degree of turbidity and solids in suspension of the must. When emitting the light on a such complex medium there will be multiple effects on beam of light, which can be summarized in three: reflection, absorption and scattering. The part of light that will reach the receiver will come from both the reflection (that which has not been absorbed) and the scattering. In any case, the wavelength that the receivers will see will be the one that has not been absorbed. Due to this complexity, it would entail a great difficulty to establish the mathematical relationship between the intensity of light emitted in each wavelength and that received by each of the photodiodes, especially because the medium is not uniform and variable from one instant to the next. Monte Carlo methods (Fang and Boas, 2009; Boas et al., 2002) could have been used to try to characterize photonic transport in this complex environment, but in our case we decided to use the "electronic eye" approach, in which learning is established of the stimulus-medium-response relationship, which allows, through statistical analysis (Apretei et al., 2010), to obtain the characteristics of the environment, analyzing only its response to the stimulus.

The obtained data were analyzed with the statistical Statgraphics Centurion XVI program. Initially for each sample, data were preprocessed and the RGB values far from the mean were removed. Once data had been filtered, the corrected sample mean and the error of each shot were obtained. Models were loaded with the corrected sample mean and the values obtained by the standardized methods (see Section 2.2) were taken as references.

Given the limited number of labels (4 per sample), a linear regression technique was used to create a multiparametric correlation model of CI and shade. Of the 97 initial samples, 11 random samples were separated to form the validation set (validation set 1) and the remaining 86 formed calibration set 1. In the studies from which the rosé wine was discarded, the validation and calibration sets consisted of 11 and 81 samples, respectively (validation set 2 and calibration set 2). Variables were optimized to obtain a better fit between the CI or shade values measured by the spectrophotometer and those obtained from the linear regression model expressed as R^2 .

An ANOVA analysis, run at a 95% confidence level, was carried out to determine the influence of diverse factors (sample date, wine type, grape variety, glass window type) on the variables of interest (color Intensity and shade), as measured by standard procedures. The analysis was applied to the residuals of samples calculated by the linear equation. The F-test in the ANOVA table determined the significant differences between means. If there were multiple levels for a certain label, multiple range tests were performed. For the parametric labels (temperature, pH and alcohol volume), Pearson's correlation was applied.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Characteristics of the samples

In order to study the effect of various experimental variables on the sensor's response, 91 samples were collected from an industrial environment and several parameters were recorded: sampling day (samples were collected from various tanks over a 7-day period), grape variety, temperature, degree of alcohol, glass window (the sensor was tested over two windows), pH, CI and shade. Table 1 summarizes the main parameters grouped according to varieties. We can see that the samples composed mainly of Syrah grapes or Monastrell and Tempranillo mixtures were the usual ones in the region from which samples were collected. Most wines corresponded to red wines with CIs between 6.7 and 9.5, but six samples of rosé wine of the bobal variety were also included with a CI round 1.5. Shade gave values that came close to 0.7 for red wines and slightly higher (0.86) ones for the bobal rosé wines. Some differences were also found in the degree of alcohol data. The Tempranillo, Syrah and Monastrell/Syrah mixtures obtained values round 13.7 degrees, and Monastrell, Tempranillo/Monastrell and Tempranillo/Tintorera/Monastrell were round 13.3 degrees. On the contrary, Bobal had a lower alcoholic degree (12.9). pH did not seem to depend on grape variety, and values between 3.4 and 3.9 were obtained. The measurements taken with the sensor were collected through two different glass windows of the same kind. The table indicates which samples were measured with each glass window.

3.2 Optical sensor

Color is the result of the light source-object-observer interaction. The sensor was applied directly to wine, including solids in suspension. The light emitted by the sensor reached the wine, it was partially absorbed by the wine according to their color and the rest reflected to photodiodes. The sensor broke the light into the three primary colors (red, green and blue), measured the reflected light and gave a value based on the difference between the quantity emitted and the quantity reflected. This difference depended on both the fluid to be measured and the material on which the sensor was based (glass type), which especially affected its thickness.

3.3 Color intensity (CI)

A linear regression model was used to model CI, and included the red and rosé wine data. The model was fed with the CI calculated from the absorbance values measured by the spectrophotometer (filtered samples) and the R, G, B and C data generated by the sensor (non filtered samples) after eliminating any abnormal atypical residues. In order to obtain the best model, not only R, G, B and C, but also combinations of the labels suggested by the software, were included in the model.

A quadratic function with four variables (R, G, B, C), thirteen coefficients and a constant was obtained (equation 1). A correlation matrix of the calculated vs. predicted CIs offered values above 0.98 and close to 1 and 0 for R^2 , the slope and the offset, respectively, which could be expected for a good fit. As the fitting parameters could be affected by the presence of two groups of points, the residual values were also included as an additional quality parameter. Figure 2a shows the graph for the calibration sets and Figure 2b for the residuals. As seen for both sets, a clear distribution of points through the diagonal was found, and residuals were homogeneously distributed within the positive and negative range, which confirmed the model's quality. If the residual for each sample were to be studied in-depth, the errors would be below 2.5%, with an average value of 0.177 points (Table 2). The maximum error was 0.517 points, which represents less than 10%.

$$\begin{aligned} IC_p = & 2.069 \cdot 10^2 - (7.065 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot R) - (3.238 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot G) + (7.867 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot B) - \\ & (3.474 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot C) - (6.699 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot R \cdot B) + (3.800 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot R \cdot C) - (1.363 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot B \cdot \\ & C) + (1.468 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot R \cdot G) - (7.867 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot R \cdot R \cdot C) + (5.088 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot R \cdot B \cdot C) - \\ & (1.381 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot C \cdot R \cdot C) + (2.041 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot R \cdot B \cdot R \cdot C) - (1.145 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot R \cdot B \cdot B \cdot C) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

To appreciate the goodness of equation 1, it was applied to validation set 1 (Figure 3a). We can see that the correlation coefficient value remained very high (0.988) and values very well fitted those obtained by the official OIV method. The average error equaled 0.194 points of color.

The ANOVA and Pearson's correlation analyses were applied to the residuals of the CIs to see if any label influenced the accuracy of the CI predictions. As expected from the good correlation obtained for our model, no labels induced significant differences for the values of the residuals (Table 3).

3.4 Shade

When the same methodology was applied to the shade values of calibration set 1, equation 2 was deduced. A quadratic function was obtained with three variables (R, B, C), seven coefficients and one constant.

$$H_p = 3.923 \cdot 10^{-1} + (8.730 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot B) - (5.420 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot G) - (2.441 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot B \cdot C) - (7.430 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot R \cdot C) + (6.074 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot B \cdot B \cdot C) + (2.433 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot C \cdot R \cdot C) - (6.315 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot R \cdot C \cdot B \cdot C) \quad (2)$$

The differences with the formula of the CIs, in terms of the number of coefficients, was due to the statistical program itself as the significant interactions between variables were added to the point at which the adjustment value did not increase. As Table 2 indicates, an R^2 of 0.828, a slope of 0.828 and an offset of 0.122 were obtained for the measured vs. calculated fit of the calibration set. For the validation set, $R^2 = 0.893$. The slope and offset were 0.873 and 0.088, respectively. Both series (calibration and validation sets) presented very low values for relative error (<2.0%), and an average value of 0.014 units. The lower values found for the fitting parameters for shade vs. the CI could indicate that the model could improve if samples were segmented into new more specific models to be developed for different kinds of samples.

By bearing such an approach into mind, the ANOVA and Pearson's correlation analyses were applied to the residuals of the shade data to detect which labels had a significant influence and could, thus, also influence our sensor. Table 3 provides the analysis results. For shade, all the labels except temperature seemed to offer significant differences. As seen from simply viewing data in Table 1, the rosé wines from the Bobal variety offered very different values to

(3)

the red wines for almost all the parameters. Thus, for shade, the analysis was repeated by leaving out the data of the rosé wines (shade model 2). In this case, we obtained a formula of the third-degree type (equation 3), which consisted of four variables (R, G, B, C), seventeen coefficients and one constant.

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_p = & -44.843 + (4.288 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot R) + (3.882 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot G) - (3.010 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot B) + (2.527 \cdot \\
 & 10^{-3} \cdot C) - (3.668 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot R \cdot G) + (2.223 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot R \cdot B) - (1.045 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot R \cdot C) - \\
 & (1.176 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot R \cdot R \cdot G) + (5.746 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot R \cdot R \cdot C) - (6.663 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot R \cdot G \cdot B) + \\
 & (2.223 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot R \cdot B \cdot C) - (6.778 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot G \cdot B) + (8.845 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot G \cdot C) + (3.184 \cdot \\
 & 10^{-9} \cdot G \cdot R \cdot G) + (4.913 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot G \cdot R \cdot C) - (2.296 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot G \cdot G \cdot B) - (1.934 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \\
 & C \cdot R \cdot C)
 \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the calibration set offered values of 0.788, 0.7873 and 0.1497 for R^2 , slope and offset, respectively. From the fitting parameters of the calibration set, a slight worsening took place with equation 3 (Figure 4a). Indeed, the average residuals and the average relative error improved by around 50% (see Table 2). With equation 3, the maximum error was 0.0476, which was below 10%. The graph of the residuals, which is representative of the error whose values were previously mentioned, is interesting (Figure 4b). We observe that the residues are randomly distributed above or below the line; that is, they take a positive or negative value indistinctly, which means that the formula adequately processes data with no tendency appearing.

The graph constructed with validation set 2 (Figure 5a), with an $R^2 = 0.67236$, presents similar adjustments. The ordinate at the origin continues to have a very low value (0.1455) and the average error is only 0.0082 points (1.21%). As observed in calibration set 2, equation 3 worsens the fitting parameters, but improves the accuracy of the analysis. The distribution of the residuals (Figure 5b) does not offer a clear trend to suggest any prediction problem.

The ANOVA and Pearson tests applied to the residuals of set 2 reveal that if the rosé wine samples are removed, most labels will be non significant with a 95% confidence level, and only

variety is significant (Table 3). Thus an additional segmentation level could be applied by variety, but the current solution seemed adequate as errors were low, which would generate additional complexity and limit practical applications.

4. Conclusions

We developed an optical sensor and algorithm capable of not only measuring wine with solids in suspension, but also of displaying the CI and shade values of the filtered samples without sampling or coming into direct contact with wine. For CI, the formula appeared robust as a good correlation was obtained for the model with the calibration set values, as verified by the low level of error for the validation set samples. Moreover for shade, a slope that came close to 1 and an ordinate in the origin that came close to 0 were obtained, although the values were not as good as for CI because the average error was relatively low. The model's accuracy for shade calculations could improve if samples were segmented and only dark wine was included. This approach undoubtedly offers several advantages over traditional analysis methods, and opens the door to automated processes in warehouses. With the calculated formulas, quality predictions can be very precise, especially for CIs, which would allow wine color to be measured during the vinification process non intrusively and non destructively. This novel technique is easy to use and manage, and is cheaper than the conventional spectrophotometer-based analysis. The small sensor size and its easy coupling to an industrial glass window allows it to be placed in all winemaking process stages and would, therefore, allow color evolution to be controlled throughout the process.

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Table 1. Reference values measured to wine samples: Tempranillo (Tp), Monastrell (Mn), Syrah (Sy), Bobal (Bo), Tintorera (Tn).

Variety	Number of samples	Day/s	Temp	Degree of alcohol	Glass window	pH	CI average (max-min)	Shade average (max-min)
Tp^a	6	1 and 3	12-15°C	13.65 ^o	M1	3.60	8.625 (8.205- 8.875)	0.674 (0.674- 0.701)
Mn^a	3	1 and 2	11-12°C	13.3	M1	3.60	9.248 (9.190- 9.320)	0.697 (0.667- 0.727)
Sy^a	49	2. 3. 4 and 6	12-19°C	13.7 ^o	20 M1 29 M2	3.57 - 3.92	8.615 (7.907- 9.525)	0.716 (0.708- 0.763)
Tn+ Tp+Mn^a	6	5	11-12°C	13.3 ^o	M1	3.53	7.973 (7.825- 8.195)	0.644 (0.633- 0.648)
Tp + Mn^a	21	4 and 5	11-13°C	13.3 ^o	M1	3.47 - 3.60	7.118 (6.748 - 7.420)	0.700 (0.654- 0.720)
Mn+ Sy^a	6	7	12-13°C	13.7 ^o	M1	3.75	8.94 (8.609- 9.06)	0.712 (0.710- 0.714)
Bo^b	6	7	13-14°C	12.9 ^o	M2	3.71	1.511 (1.450- 1.555)	0.860 (0.841- 0.880)

Table 2: Adjusting parameters (slope, offset, R^2 , average residuals and relative error) from the correlations between the calculated and measured values for the calibration and validation sets.

Parameter	Set	Slope	Offset	R^2	Average residuals	Average relative error
Color	Calibration 1	0.9844	0.1195	0.9803	0.1770	2.38
Color	Validation 1	0.9349	0.4700	0.9879	0.1940	3.23
Shade	Calibration 1	0.8284	0.1221	0.8284	0.0140	1.97
Shade	Validation 1	0.8734	0.0879	0.8930	0.0140	1.97
Shade	Calibration 2	0.7873	0.1497	0.7880	0.0059	0.84
Shade	Validation 2	0.7965	0.1455	0.6724	0.0082	1.21

Table 3. Statistical analysis of the residuals

Label	Analysis	P-value		
		Color intensity	Shade 1	Shade 2
Sampling day	ANOVA	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05
Wine type	ANOVA	>0.05	0.0309	NA
Variety	ANOVA	>0.05	0.0000	0.0254
Glass window	ANOVA	>0.05	0.0012	>0.05
Temperature	Pearson	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05
Alcohol	Pearson	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05
pH	Pearson	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05
Number of samples		97 (86)	86	81

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1: a) detail of the sensor. b) scheme of the sensor. c) detail of the sensor placed at the measurement point

Figure 2: a) CI calculated vs. CI measured in calibration set 1. b) residuals

Figure 3: a) CI calculated vs. CI measured in validation set 1. b) residuals

Figure 4: a) Shade calculated vs. shade measured in calibration set 2. b) residuals

Figure 5: a) Shade calculated vs. shade measured in validation set 2. b) residuals

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

